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Research Article

Formulation and *in vitro* evaluation of moxifloxacin hydrochloride ophthalmic inserts

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Abstract

Moxifloxacin hydrochloride is a fluoroquinolone anti-infective agent useful in the treatment of eye infection such as conjunctivitis, keratitis and keratoconjunctivitis. An attempt has been made to formulate ophthalmic insert of moxifloxacin hydrochloride using hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (4-7%), methylcellulose (2-3.5%) and polyvinyl alcohol (4-7%) as polymers by solvent casting method with aim of increasing the contact time, achieving controlled release, reduction in frequency of administration and greater therapeutic efficacy. The prepared ophthalmic insert were then evaluated for uniformity of thickness, weight, drug content, % moisture absorption, % moisture loss, folding endurance and surface pH. *In vitro* drug release of formulated batches of ophthalmic insert was performed by studying the diffusion through artificial membrane (prehydrated cellophane). FTIR spectroscopy was performed to study the interaction of drug in formulation using KBr disc method. On the basis of all physicochemical parameters and *in vitro* drug release studies, the formulation (F12) with PVA (7%) was found to be promising and it was selected as an optimized formulation. The result of *in vitro* diffusion study of promising formulation (F12) exhibited first order kinetic, which is non-fickian in nature. The Higuchi plot revealed that the release might be diffusion controlled.

Keywords: Moxifloxacin hydrochloride, ophthalmic inserts, HPMC, MC, PVA, *in vitro* release

Introduction

The ophthalmic delivery of drugs continues to be challenged by the intrinsic physiology of the eye. The efficient removal mechanism that operate at the site of action (rapid tear turn over, blinking) and the low corneal permeability act cooperatively to suppress the effectiveness of ophthalmic formulations and to limit drug bioavailability to less than 5%.¹ Moreover, systemic absorption of the drug and additives drained through nasolacrimal duct may result in undesirable effects. An effective way to achieve slow and prolonged absorption in ophthalmic practice is to incorporate a drug into a polymeric film, which when placed in the cul-de-sac of the eye exhibits a prolonged local release for drug action on tissue in the immediate vicinity.²

Moxifloxacin hydrochloride (HCl) is a new 8-methoxy derivate of fluoroquinolones with enhanced activity invitro against gram

positive bacteria and maintenance of activity against gram negative bacteria³. It is an anti-infective agent useful in the treatment of eye infection such as bacterial conjunctivitis, keratitis and keratoconjunctivitis. It is presently available as eye drops 0.5% (Vigamox, Alcon lab.). It is administered at dosing interval of 1 drop in the affected eye 3 times a day for 7 days⁴ The eye drop type dosage form is convenient to use but most of the drug is diluted by tear and rapidly washed out of the sac by constant tear flow which can be avoided by using insert by which the therapeutic efficacy of ophthalmic drug can greatly improved⁵. Attempts have been made by researchers in order to prepare ophthalmic insert by solvent casting technique using hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), methylcellulose (MC) and polyvinyl alcohol with swellable polymeric excipients^{6,7}. In the present study, an attempt has been made to formulate ophthal-

mic insert of moxifloxacin hydrochloride using hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), methylcellulose (MC) and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) as polymers and polyethylene glycol 400 (PEG 400)⁷ as plasticizer by solvent casting method.

Material and methods

Materials

Moxifloxacin hydrochloride (% Purity - 99.6%) was obtained as gift sample from Torrent pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd., Gandhinagar. Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC 15 cps), methylcellulose (MC 400 cps) and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA mw 14,000) were obtained from SD Fine chemicals, Mumbai. All other reagents and solvent used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of ophthalmic insert

The inserts were prepared by solvent casting method⁸. The polymeric solution were prepared by dissolving HPMC (4 to 7%), MC (2 to 3.5 %) and PVA (4 to 7%) in distilled water (10 ml) and PEG 400 (30% w/w of polymer) was added as plasticizer to this solution under stirring condition. The weighed amount of moxifloxacin hydrochloride (253 mg) was added to above dispersion. After proper mixing the casting solution (5 ml) was poured in clean glass petridish (an area of 63.59 cm²). The petridish was dried at room temperature for 24 h. The dried films thus obtained were cut by cork borer into circular pieces of definite size 8 mm diameter (an area of 0.5024 cm²) containing of 1 mg of drug.^{9, 10, 11} The ophthalmic inserts were stored in an airtight container (desiccator) under ambient condition⁵. The formulae for different formulations are shown in the Table-1.

Evaluation of the prepared formulations

Uniformity of thickness

The thickness of the film was measured at three different spots using digital vernier calipers (Mitutoyo, Japan).¹²

Uniformity of weight

For uniformity of weight, 3 films from each batch were taken randomly and their weights were determined using electronic balance (Asco, India).¹³

Drug content

Three films were taken from each batch and dissolved or crushed in 10 ml of isotonic phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) in a beaker and were filtered into 25 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to the mark with buffer. One ml of the above sample was withdrawn and the absorbance was measured by UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Systronics - 2202, India) at 287.6 nm after suitable dilutions.¹⁴

% Moisture absorption

The percentage moisture absorption test was carried out to check physical stability or integrity of the film at humid condition. The study was carried out as per procedure reported earlier (Dhanaraju et al., 2002) The films were weighed and placed in desiccator (8x 6 inch, polylab, India) containing 100 ml of saturated solution of aluminium chloride and 80% humidity was maintained. After three days, the films were taken out and re-weighed.¹² The % moisture absorption was calculated using the formulae

$$\% \text{ Moisture absorption} = \frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100 \quad [1]$$

% Moisture loss

The percentage moisture loss was carried out to check the integrity of the film at dry condition. The films were weighted and kept in dessicator (8x 6 inch, polylab, India) containing anhydrous calcium chloride. After three days, the films were taken out and re-weighed.¹⁵ The percentage moisture loss was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Moisture loss} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100 \quad [2]$$

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Table 1: The formulae of the ingredients used in twelve batches.

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
Drug (mg)	253	253	253	253	253	253	253	253	253	253	253	253
HPMC (g)	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
MC (g)	---	---	---	---	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.35	---	---	---	---
PVA (g)	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
PEG400 (g) (30% w/w of polymers)	0.12	0.15	0.18	0.21	0.06	0.075	0.09	0.10 5	0.12	0.15	0.18	0.21
Water (g)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

Folding endurance

Three film of each formulation of size (2 x 2 cm) were cut by using sharp blade. Folding endurance was determined by repeatedly folding a small strip of the film at the same place till it broke. The number of times the film could be folded at the same place without breaking gave the value of folding endurance.¹⁶ A mean of three reading were recorded.

Surface pH

The inserts were allowed to swell in closed petridish at room temperature for 30 minutes in 0.1 ml of bidistilled water. The swollen device was removed and placed under digital pH meter (Elico, India) to determine the surface pH.¹⁷

Drug - Excipients compatibility study

The spectra were recorded for pure drug and drug loaded ophthalmic insert using FTIR (Perkin-Elmer, Spectrum GX, USA). Samples were prepared in KBr disks (2 mg sample in 200 mg KBr). The scanning range was 400 - 4000 cm^{-1} and the resolution was 2 cm^{-1} .

In vitro diffusion studies

The *in vitro* diffusion of drug from the different ophthalmic insert was studied using the classical standard cylindrical tube fabricated in the laboratory. A simple modification of glass tube of 15mm internal diame-

ter and 100 mm height¹⁶ (Figure 1). The diffusion cell membrane (prehydrated cellophane) was tied to one end of open cylinder, which acted as a donor compartment. An ophthalmic insert was placed inside this compartment. The diffusion cell membrane acted as corneal epithelium. The entire surface of the membrane was in contact with the receptor compartment comprising of 25 ml of isotonic phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) in a 100 ml beaker. The content of receptor compartment was stirred continuously using a magnetic stirrer and temperature was maintained at $37^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. At specific intervals of time, 1 ml aliquot of solution was withdrawn from the receptor compartment and replaced with fresh buffer solution. The aliquot was analyzed for the drug content using UV-VIS spectrophotometer at 287.6 nm after appropriate dilutions against reference using isotonic phosphate buffer pH 7.4 as blank.¹⁸

Mechanism and kinetics of drug release from an ophthalmic insert

In order to understand the mechanism and kinetics of drug release, the results of the *in vitro* drug release study were fitted with various kinetic equations like first order ($\log\%$ unrelease vs t), Higuchi matrix ($\%$ release vs square root of time), In order to define a model which will represent a better fit for the formulation, drug release data further analysed by Peppas equation, $M_t/M_\infty=kt^n$, where M_t is the amount of drug released at time t and M_∞ is the amount re-

leased at time ∞ , the M_t/M_∞ is the fraction of drug released at time t , k is the kinetic constant and n is the diffusional exponent, a measure of the primary mechanism of drug release. r^2 values were calculated for the linear curves obtained by regression analysis of the above plots.¹⁹

Result and Discussion

Uniformity of thickness

The prepared films were evaluated for the thickness using vernier calipers. The average of three readings was taken. The mean thickness and standard deviation were calculated. The low standard deviation of the measured thickness of all the 12 formulations may indicate uniform distribution of drug and excipients in prepared inserts. It was found to be in the range of 0.045 ± 0.006 mm to 0.120 ± 0.0043 mm (Table 2).

Uniformity of weight

The weights of all the films were found to be in the range of 7.13 ± 0.025 to 9.65 ± 0.023 mg (Table 2). The uniformity of the weights of the films indicates good distribution of the drug, polymer and plasticizer.

Drug content

For the various formulations, drug content was found to vary between 0.955 ± 0.075 to 0.992 ± 0.018 mg as shown in Table 2. The estimation of drug content was found to be almost same with their low standard deviation values.

% Moisture absorption

The % moisture absorption was calculated for all 12 formulations in triplicate (Table 2). According to the results obtained, the moisture absorption is more in the formulations in which hydrophilic polymers are present. Formulation F4 has shown maximum % moisture absorption, $12.13 \pm 0.48\%$, which may be due to the presence of HPMC which is relatively more hydrophilic in nature. The formulation F9 has shown the minimum % moisture absorption, $5.48 \pm 0.50\%$, as it contains polymer of less hydrophilic nature. It can be concluded that the HPMC and MC have more tendency to absorb moisture as compared to PVA. At humid conditions, there was more moisture absorption but there was

no change in integrity, which was observed by its physical appearance.

% Moisture loss

The % moisture loss was calculated for all the 12 formulations in triplicate (Table 2). It was observed that when the formulations were kept at very dry condition, the maximum moisture loss occurred. The formulation F9 showed maximum moisture loss of 13.94 ± 0.78 and formulation F4 showed minimum moisture loss of 8.45 ± 0.95 . The formulations containing PVA had more tendencies to lose moisture as compared to those containing HPMC and MC.

Folding endurance

The folding endurance was measured manually by folding the film repeatedly at a point till they broke. The breaking time was considered as the end point. Folding endurance was found to be highest for F12 (358.33 ± 5.96) and lowest for F4 (241.00 ± 6.99) as shown in Table 2. It was found that folding endurance of films was increased by the different polymers in following order; PVA>MC>HPMC. The folding endurance values of the film were found to be optimum and therefore the film exhibited good physical and mechanical properties.

Surface pH

The surface pH of prepared inserts was found to be in range of 6.13 to 7.14 (Table 2). This indicates that the prepared inserts would not alter the pH of the tear fluid in the eye.

Drug - Excipients compatibility study

The optimized formulation F12 and the pure drug were subjected to the FTIR analysis. The peak at 3528 nm indicating the -NH stretching, two peaks at 1708 nm and 1623 nm for the -C=O stretching of -COO and -COOH group respectively. The peaks at 1516 nm, 994 nm, and 803 nm represent the major peaks for drug. All the above peaks are also present in drug loaded ophthalmic insert that confirms the presence of drug in the polymer without any interaction.

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Table 2: Physicochemical data of ophthalmic inserts

Form.Co de	Weight* (mg)	Thickness* (mm)	Drug content* ^S (mg)	% Moisture absorption*	% Moisture loss*	Folding Endurance*	Surface pH
F1	7.16 ± 0.03	0.065 ± 0.004	0.978 ± 0.072	8.24 ± 0.70	12.10 ± 0.75	265.33 ± 4.93	6.83
F2	8.55 ± 0.040	0.080 ± 0.007	0.981 ± 0.076	9.76 ± 0.64	11.56 ± 0.32	276.33 ± 4.23	6.76
F3	8.94 ± 0.047	0.084 ± 0.005	0.978 ± 0.062	11.33 ± 0.45	9.27 ± 0.41	290.67 ± 5.82	6.56
F4	8.30 ± 0.035	0.120 ± 0.043	0.986 ± 0.071	12.13 ± 0.48	8.45 ± 0.95	241.00 ± 6.99	6.13
F5	9.10 ± 0.035	0.045 ± 0.006	0.968 ± 0.045	7.44 ± 0.59	13.50 ± 0.60	315.00 ± 4.10	6.60
F6	8.96 ± 0.08	0.063 ± 0.005	0.985 ± 0.065	8.39 ± 0.77	13.12 ± 1.4	326.67 ± 5.47	6.25
F7	9.65 ± 0.023	0.070 ± 0.009	0.962 ± 0.035	9.41 ± 0.65	11.32 ± 0.53	331.67 ± 5.39	6.90
F8	8.38 ± 0.042	0.089 ± 0.007	0.979 ± 0.021	10.56 ± 0.87	9.86 ± 0.86	342.00 ± 4.73	6.67
F9	7.13 ± 0.025	0.052 ± 0.010	0.985 ± 0.035	5.48 ± 0.50	13.94 ± 0.78	328.00 ± 6.26	6.25
F10	8.16 ± 0.041	0.074 ± 0.005	0.955 ± 0.075	6.75 ± 0.61	12.53 ± 0.34	339.00 ± 5.59	6.50
F11	8.30 ± 0.046	0.079 ± 0.011	0.985 ± 0.034	7.13 ± 0.90	11.54 ± 1.21	345.67 ± 4.23	6.00
F12	7.78 ± 0.039	0.096 ± 0.007	0.992 ± 0.018	7.86 ± 0.52	10.39 ± 0.24	358.33 ± 5.96	7.14

* mean ± SD (n=3)
^S (The theoretical drug content is 1 mg in an area of 0.5024 cm²)

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Table 3: Kinetic data of Drug Release from F1 to F12

Formulation Code	First order		Higuchi model		Krosemeyer Peppas model	
	K_1	r^2	K_h	r^2	n	r^2
F1	-0.0117	0.9875	5.969	0.9798	0.501	0.9707
F2	-0.0103	0.9960	5.481	0.9767	0.531	0.9880
F3	-0.0088	0.9789	5.011	0.9623	0.574	0.9738
F4	-0.0071	0.9931	4.992	0.9627	0.640	0.9828
F5	-0.0158	0.9619	6.553	0.9803	0.463	0.9734
F6	-0.0122	0.9694	5.929	0.9577	0.525	0.9512
F7	-0.0113	0.9726	5.499	0.9577	0.579	0.9708
F8	-0.0096	0.9473	5.469	0.9685	0.605	0.9817
F9	-0.0088	0.9747	5.309	0.9954	0.489	0.9928
F10	-0.0081	0.9888	5.262	0.9965	0.536	0.9978
F11	-0.0062	0.9994	4.868	0.9939	0.554	0.9958
F12	-0.0053	0.9939	4.749	0.9894	0.608	0.9935

K: release rate constant; r^2 : Coefficient of determination; n: release exponent

Figure 1: *In vitro* diffusion assembly

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Figure 2: *In vitro* diffusion of Moxifloxacin HCl from F1 to F12 formulations

***In vitro* diffusion studies**

The percentage drug release of all the formulations is presented in Figure 2. The formulation which showed better physico-chemical parameters with prolonged release was selected. Out of 12 formulations (F1 to F12) tried, the formulation F12 containing PVA (7%) was found to be promising, since it showed prolonged release with 91.73% at end of 7 h. The prolonged release may be probably due to the formation of hydrogen bonds between the drug and polymers which have helped in rate control release of drug⁷.

Mechanism and kinetics of drug release from an ophthalmic insert

The *in vitro* release profile was analyzed by various kinetic models. The kinetic models used were first order, Higuchi and Krosmeier Peppas equations (Table 3). The release constants were calculated from the

slope of the respective plots. It indicates that the release of drug from the films might have followed first order kinetics. Higher correlation was observed in the Higuchi equation. For planer geometry, the value of $n=0.5$ indicates a Fickian diffusion mechanism, for $0.5 < n < 1.0$, indicates anomalous (non-fickian) transport, and $n=1$ implies case II (relaxation controlled) transport¹⁹. In the present systems, the value for n was found to be in the range of 0.463 to 0.640 indicating that the release mechanisms followed fickian diffusion and anomalous (non-fickian) transport. The optimized formulation (F12) was having $n=0.608$, indi-

cating that the release mechanism followed is non-fickian diffusion controlled mechanism.

Conclusion

The formulation of ophthalmic insert containing moxifloxacin hydrochloride and PVA (7%) seems to be promising and further *in vivo* study must be carried out to check the efficacy of preparations.

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